

Productivity and the Qualitative Response of Sorghum to Different Planting Patterns and Various Cultivars

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Funding Information
No funding

Received: 28-02-2022
Revised: 15-03-2022
Accepted: 16-03-2022

Abstract

Planting patterns and different cultivars play a significant role in forage crops quality and productivity. Therefore, we conducted a field experiment under different planting patterns and cultivars to evaluate sorghum crop yield, yield components, and quality at Agronomic Research Farm, Department of Agronomy, University of Agriculture Faisalabad, Pakistan, in 2015. The experiment consists of three sorghum cultivars (Jawar 2002, Sorghum-2011, and JS-2002) with a seed rate of 75 kg ha⁻¹ at different planting patterns (P1=60 cm × 20 cm, P2=50cm × 24 cm, and P3=340 cm × 30 cm). Results showed that sorghum 2011 resulted in higher growth and qualitative attributes than other cultivars. For example, increase in plant height (237.11 cm), dry weight plant⁻¹ (40.61 g), forage yield (57.66 ton ha⁻¹), crude protein contents (6.12 %), fiber contents (32.12 %) and ash contents (8.73%) was observed in sorghum 2011 as compared to other cultivars. Whereas, among planting pattern P₃ (40 x 30 cm) produced maximum plant height (236.33 cm), leaves plant⁻¹(13.66), stem diameter (1.09 cm), forage yield (55.52 ton ha⁻¹), dry matter yield (18.53 ton ha⁻¹) and crude protein contents (6.06 %) as compared to P1 and P2. This study suggested that the cultivar sorghum 2011 with a planting pattern of 40 x 30 cm is a promising option to improve yield, yield components and quality of sorghum crop.

Keywords: Sorghum, Planting pattern, Cultivars, Crude Protein, Fiber content

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1. Introduction

Agriculture is the most important sector of Pakistan and greatly influences economic growth. It accounts for 21.4% of GDP and 45% of employment is engaged with agriculture (Gecho, 2017, Iqbal et al., 2015). Development in the agriculture sector stimulates growth in the agro-industry, especially the textile sector. Livestock is an important agriculture sector and has a

central role in our country's rural economy. Its accounts for 54% of agricultural GDP and 11.9% of total GDP (Mehmood et al., 2020, Jahnke and Jahnke, 1982). Sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* L.) is a member of the Poaceae family is locally called Jawar and is commonly used as fresh, silage or hay form. Sorghum is a dual-purpose (i.e., grown for grain and fodder yield) summer season crop (Hedayetullah and Zaman, 2018; Sarfraz et